

Studies on the Energy Transfer Reactions in the Gas Phase. Part I. The Cadmium Photosensitised Cis-Trans Isomerization of Butene-2 at 265°*

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The cadmium photosensitised cis-trans isomerization of butene-2 has been studied in the gas phase at 265° with a view to finding out its suitability as an actinometer in the cadmium photosensitised reactions of hydrocarbons. Detail analytical investigations have been made with a gas chromatograph and a mass spectrometer. The major reaction product of cis-butene-2 at 265° in the presence of cadmium vapor and at $\lambda = 3261 \text{ \AA}$ radiation, is trans-butene-2, while the very minor products detected are H_2 , CH_4 , C_2H_6 , and C_2H_4 . This cis-trans reaction of butene-2 under the experimental conditions appears to be clean and is found to be suitable for actinometry in the cadmium photosensitised reactions.

The measured (k_1/k_0) ratio = 3.15×10^5 liter/mole. The quenching rate constant (k_1) is therefore 1.60×10^{11} liter/mole/sec. at 538°K, if the radiative life time ($1/k_0$) is 2.0×10^{-6} secs. This gives 15.4 Sq. A. as the quenching cross section. However if the radiative life time is 10^{-4} secs as reported recently by Strausz et al, k_1 becomes 3.15×10^9 liter/mole/sec, which leads to 0.302 Sq. A. as the quenching cross section. This value of k_1 is in good agreement with the quenching rate constant of the corresponding ethylene reaction,

THE Cadmium photosensitised reactions of olefins were first studied by LeRoy and Steacie¹, who measured the quenching cross sections of olefins with respect to $\text{Cd}(^3\text{P}_1) \rightarrow \text{Cd}(^1\text{S}_0)$ transition at 213° by a photophysical process. The quenching cross section of butene-2 was found to be about 30.6 sq.A., if the radiative life time of $\text{Cd}(^3\text{P}_1)$ is 2.0×10^{-6} secs. Recently Tsunashima and Sato^{2,3} have reported the cadmium and the mercury photosensitised isomerization of butene-2 at 275° to 350° (which is also the temperature controlling the cadmium concentration in the reaction vessel), and have measured the quenching efficiencies of a variety of gases relative to the quenching rate constant of cis-butene-2 normalised to unity.

The purpose of the present investigation is to find out whether the cis-trans isomerization of butene-2 would be an ideal actinometer in the energy transfer

study of the cadmium photosensitised decompositions of paraffins, olefins and cycloparaffins.

Experimental

All gaseous hydrocarbons used were of Phillips Research grade and were subsequently purified by means of preparative gas chromatography. Other hydrocarbons used for G.C. calibration were supplied by the Matheson Chemicals Inc., while the ultrapure hydrogen was supplied by Air products (U.S.A.). Hydrogen from the cylinder was passed through an evacuated U-tube packed with silica gel at liquid nitrogen temperature to remove traces of oxygen. Mass Spectrometric analysis showed that the amount of oxygen present in the purified hydrogen was less than $10^{-6}\%$.

Cadmium (99.90%) pure was supplied by Matheson, Coleman and Bell. The impurities present were stated to be Zn (0.05%), Pb (0.05%), Fe (0.01%) and Cu (0.005%). A Cadmium lamp (Osram spectral

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lamp) was used in series with a SOLA—constant voltage transformer.

The reaction was carried out in a cylindrical pyrex vessel (5" in length and 1.75" in diameter) at 265° ± 0.5° in a conventional static system. The vessel was connected to a Hg-free vacuum line via capillary pyrex tubing. The cadmium was kept in a side arm (1/4" dia. pyrex tubing), which was heated separately by another movable electrically heated and controlled furnace. The trapped gases from the cadmium metal were removed by distillation under high vacuum. A Photomultiplier Microphotometer (AMINCO, Silver Spring, Maryland, U.S.A.) was used to check the concentration of cadmium vapour in the reaction cell, and also the lamp intensity. The cadmium lamp was cooled by nitrogen so as to get reproducible results. The reproducibility in the rates of product formation was not better than ±10%, but the product distribution was found to be independent of lamp intensity, and highly reproducible (i.e., better than ±3%).

Product analyses were carried out by a gas chromatograph and a double focussing mass-spectrometer. The gas chromatograph was integrated with the reaction system and the vacuum line via a 6-ports stainless steel automatic gas sampling valve (Varian Aerograph). The G.C. had a very sensitive flame ionization detector, which could see easily as little as 10⁻⁹ (moles/liter) hydrocarbons in the mixture gas samples. The non-condensables at the liquid nitrogen temperature were collected from the reaction cell by a Toepler pump, connected to the vacuum line via a series of liquid nitrogen traps, and were analysed mass spectrometrically.

The reaction cell was evacuated to 10⁻⁵ torr, and the side arm temperature was adjusted so as to get the desired concentration of Cd vapor in the reaction cell, the temperature of which was always kept at 265°. The Cd-lamp was warmed up for 1 hr, and the desired lamp intensity was adjusted by cooling with nitrogen. The reactant (thoroughly degassed, fractionated and analysed by G.C.) at a desired pressure (measured either by a Wallace-Tiernan pressure gauge or by the pressure sharing device), was introduced into the reaction cell. Half an hour later, the mixture of the reactant and the cadmium vapor was exposed to irradiation. After a measured time, of illumination, the lamp was switched off. Half an hour later, the gas mixtures were analysed by G.C. and mass spectrometry.

Results

The effective radiation under the experimental conditions is the 3261 Å wave length (λ) light. At about 0.55 torr of cis-butene-2-pressure, the photomultiplier readings indicated total quenching of the resonance fluorescence. Dark reactions with 2 torr cis-butene-2 and 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ torr cadmium vapor were carried out for 3 hr at 265° but no products were detected. Similarly, when cis-butene-2 was exposed to 3261 Å radiation in the absence of cadmium vapor at 265° for 5 hr, no products were found. This confirms the observation of Sato *et al.*³ that the cis-

trans isomerisation of butene-2 is due to the interaction of the hot cadmium atoms (³P₁) with the butene-2 molecules.

The major product under the experimental conditions is trans-butene-2, while the minor products are H₂, CH₄, and C₂H₆. By photolysing of 0.779 torr cis-butene-2 (measured by the pressure sharing device) in the presence of 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ torr cadmium vapor for 3 hr at 265°, the following products were found :

Trans-butene-2	= 0.137 torr
Methane	= 2.64 × 10 ⁻⁸ (moles/liter)
Hydrogen	= 15.21 × 10 ⁻⁸ (moles/liter)
Propylene	= very small (not estimated)
Ethane	= trace (≈ 10 ⁻⁹ moles/liter).
and unreacted cis-butene-2	= 0.633 torr.

It is clear that the formation of minor products at very low extent of reaction is not significant from the kinetic and mechanistic standpoints of the isomerization reaction of butene-2. The rates of formation of trans-butene-2 under different experimental conditions were only measured at different cadmium vapor pressure viz., 9.0 × 10⁻⁵ and 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ torr, and in the pressure range 0.033 to 2.0 torr cis-butene-2. Some typical results are presented in Table 1 and

TABLE 1—CADMIUM VAPOR PRESSURE ≈ 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ TORR CORRESPONDING TO (213° ± 1°), AND THE REACTION VESSEL TEMPERATURE 265°

Time of photolysis (hrs.)	Cis-butene-2 pressure (torr) measured by the pressure sharing device	Trans-butene-2 (torr) measured by G.C. (a)	Unreacted cis-butene-2 (torr) measured by G.C. (b)	Total (torr) (a+b)
1.00	0.9735	6.00 × 10 ⁻²	0.900	0.9600
1.00	0.9735	6.20 × 10 ⁻²	0.933	0.9950
0.50	0.9735	3.16 × 10 ⁻²	0.937	0.9686
0.25	0.9735	1.57 × 10 ⁻²	0.960	0.9757
0.50	1.463	3.10 × 10 ⁻²	1.430	1.4610
0.50	2.000	3.15 × 10 ⁻²	1.970	2.0015
1.00	0.420	4.34 × 10 ⁻²	0.370	0.4134
1.00	0.390	4.15 × 10 ⁻²	0.345	0.3865
Cadmium vapour pressure ≈ 9.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ torr, corresponding to (180 ± 1)°C				
0.25	0.98	0.535 × 10 ⁻²	0.980	0.9853
0.50	0.98	1.100 × 10 ⁻²	0.955	0.9660
0.75	0.98	1.710 × 10 ⁻²	0.980	0.9771
1.00	0.98	2.250 × 10 ⁻²	0.950	0.9725

Note : This Table shows only few a typical yield—time data. The agreement between the initial reactant pressure measured by the pressure sharing device and the total pressure of trans-butene-2 and the unreacted cis-butene-2 measured by G.C., is clearly excellent within the experimental error (±5%).

Figure 1, which show clearly that upto 6% conversion, trans-butene-2 is formed at a constant rate. From such figures, initial rates of trans-butene-2

formation under different experimental conditions were determined, and the results are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2—CADMIUM VAPOR PRESSURE $\approx 9.0 \times 10^{-4}$ TORR; REACTION VESSEL AT 265°

Cis-butene-2 (m/l) $\times 10^7$	Trans-butene-2 (m/l/hr) $\times 10^7$ i.e. $R_t \times 10^7$	1/(cis-butene) in (l/m) $\times 10^{-4}$	$1/R_t \times 10^{-7}$ l.hr./m
290.00	6.55	3.45	0.153
575.00	6.87	1.74	0.150
129.00	5.57	7.75	0.180
47.40	4.14	21.30	0.242
10.00	1.915	100.00	0.523

Cadmium vapor pressure $\approx 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ torr; reaction vessel at 265°

Cad. vapor pressure (torr)	Trans-butene-2 (m/l/hr) $\times 10^7$	1/(cis-butene) (l/m) $\times 10^{-4}$	$1/R_t \times 10^{-7}$ (l.hr./m)
15.30	5.98	65.4	0.168
32.80	8.75	30.5	0.114
121.00	15.25	8.24	0.0656
145.00	16.65	6.90	0.0601
288.00	18.85	3.47	0.0532
435.00	18.50	2.30	0.054
596.00	18.80	1.675	0.0532

Note: Not all the yield-time curves are shown in Fig. 1. Initial rates of trans-butene-2 formation were determined from these yield-time curves, and the results are summarised in Table 2.

From Fig. 2, the following results were extracted

Cadmium vapor pressure in torr.	Rate of light absorption (I_a) in einstein/ml/sec.	(k_1/k_0) (liter/mole)
5.0×10^{-4}	11.10×10^{-13}	2.57×10^6
9.0×10^{-5}	3.90×10^{-13}	3.73×10^6

Discussion

The mechanism of cis-trans isomerization of olefins in the gas phase has been discussed by Cundall⁴ and by Benson⁵ at length, and need not be discussed here. For the kinetic treatment, it will be assumed that there is no surface reaction and the electronically excited cis-butene-2 molecules are formed by the collision with the hot cadmium (3P_1) atoms. By analogy with the triplet $Hg(^3P_1)$ -butene-2 reactions, the important elementary reactions believed to be occurring in the cadmium system are:

where ϕ_a is the quantum yield of the reaction (a).

Since trans-butene-2 is formed at a constant rate initially, it is assumed that the reaction

is not significant kinetically at low conversion; therefore, this reaction is not included into the reaction mechanism. The symbol (*) denotes electronic excitation. Assuming steady state, and $k_3 = k_2$,

Fig. 1. Yield-time curves of trans-butene-2 formation under different experimental conditions.

which does not appear unreasonable^{2,3}, it follows from the Stern-Volmer treatment that

$$1/R_t = 2(k_b/k_1)\{1/[\phi_a I_a(\text{cis-butene})]\} + 2/\phi_a I_a$$

where $\phi_a = 1.0$ for the reaction (a); $I_a =$ rate of light absorption in the process (a), and R_t denotes the rate of trans-butene-2 formation. Since the quantum yield (ϕ_a) is unity, the Stern-Volmer equation becomes

$$1/R_t = 2(k_b/k_1)\{1/[I_a(\text{cis-butene})]\} + 2/I_a \quad \dots (1)$$

Some plots according to equation (1) are shown in the figure 2. From the slopes and intercepts of these linear plots, it is found that $(k_1/k_b) = 2.57 \times 10^5$ (liter/mole) at cadmium pressure 5.0×10^{-4} torr, and is equal to 3.75×10^5 (liter/mole) when the cadmium pressure is 9.0×10^{-5} torr. The average of $(k_1/k_b) = 3.15 \times 10^5$ (liter/mole). The quenching rate constant (k_1) is therefore 1.60×10^{11} liter/mole/sec at 538°K, if the radiative life time ($1/k_b$) of $\text{Cd}(^3\text{P}_1)$ is 2.0×10^{-6} secs, as reported by Calvert and Pitts (Jr.)⁶. The quenching cross section is found to be 15.4 sq.Å. This value is less than that reported by Steacie and LeRoy in the early forties by a factor of 2. This type of discrepancy is probably due to the methods used in measuring the quenching rate constant, and is also found in the Hg system⁶. Our results⁷ indicate that both the hydrogen and the ethylene have the same efficiency in quenching the $\text{Cd}(^3\text{P}_1)$ to the ground state, and this is in agreement with the findings of Sato *et al.*^{2,3}. Steacie and LeRoy however reported that the quenching rate constant of ethylene in the cadmium system is twice that of hydrogen.

Recently Strausz *et al.*¹² reported the radiative life time of $\text{Cd}(^3\text{P}_1)$ as 1.0×10^{-4} secs from the flash

photolysis studies of dimethyl cadmium, and the quenching rate constant (k) of ethylene for the reaction $\text{Cd}(^3\text{P}_1) + \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 \rightarrow \text{Cd}(^1\text{S}_0) + \text{C}_2\text{H}_4^*$ as $k = 2.0 \times 10^9$ (liter/mole/sec). If $(1/k_b)$ is taken as 10^{-4} secs, then k_1 for cis-butene-2 becomes 3.15×10^9 (liter/mole/sec). The ratio of $k_1/k = 3.15 \times 10^9/2.0 \times 10^9 = 1.58$; which agrees fairly well with that in the Hg system¹³, viz :

$$k_B/k_A = (40.0 \times 10^{10})/(30.0 \times 10^{10}) = 1.33.$$

The work of Strausz *et al.* shows clearly that the old work of Steacie and LeRoy is not reliable.

It is surprising that hydrogen is a minor product in the cadmium system. In the case of $\text{Hg}(^3\text{P}_1) - \text{C}_4\text{H}_8-2$ system, hydrogen has been shown² to be formed by a molecular process as well as from the H-atom and cis-butene-2 reaction. In the cadmium system the reaction

is exothermic to the extent of about 50 kcal/mole at 298°K (relevant data taken from reference 6), and is therefore likely to occur, but the analytical data show that the methyl acetylenes are not the products of the reaction.

The mechanism of formation of hydrogen and other products is not clear. This would require more

Fig. 2. Plot of $1/[\text{trans-butene}]$ in (l.hr.m^{-2}) versus $1/[\text{cis-butene}]$ in (l.m^{-2})

analytical data on the formations of minor products, which are hard to get with precision at very low extent of reactions. It may be relevant to mention here that the pressure broadening effect is not important in the case of cadmium upto 10^{-3} torr as reported by Sato *et al.*^{2,3}. In contrast, the pressure broadening effect is more pronounced in the case of Hg as reported by Sato *et al.* and by Yang⁸. If this is so, then the kinetic data extracted from the Hg-alkane system^{9,10} are not reliable and have to be accepted with considerable reservation. The situation is further complicated by the formation of Hg(³P₁) atoms¹¹ whose role in the Hg-alkane system is not yet clearly understood.

In conclusion it may be stated that the Cd(³P₁)-butene-2 reaction is much cleaner than that of the Hg(³P₁)-butene-2. The former may be used as an actinometer in the cadmium photosensitised reactions.

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